

Effects of liquid fuel/wall interaction on thermoacoustic instabilities in swirling spray flames

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Abstract

Computational prediction of thermoacoustic instabilities arising in gas turbine and aero-engine combustors still remains a challenge especially if fuel is injected in a liquid spray form. This study shows that, in the LES of these combustors, the treatment of the liquid fuel film created on the walls of the injection system affects the mean flame weakly but modifies the flame dynamics strongly. The configuration used for this work is the experimental setup SICCA-spray measured at EM2C laboratory in Paris. First steady spray flame measurements are used to validate the LES Euler-Lagrange approach. Two modeling strategies for the interaction between the liquid fuel and the injector walls are tested with a negligible impact on the flame shape and structure showing an equivalence between taking into account or neglecting the presence of a liquid film layer on the injector walls. In the second part the same comparison is applied to another operating condition where a self-sustained thermo-acoustic limit-cycle is experimentally observed. In that case resonant coupling is achieved with LES, confirming the adequacy of the approach but only when the film layer is taken into account. Indeed, contrarily to the stable configuration, the difference between the two Lagrangian boundary conditions is shown to have a major impact on the feedback mechanism leading to the thermoacoustic oscillation.

Keywords: Combustion, Thermoacoustic instabilities, Two-phase flows

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1. Introduction

Modern gas turbines operating in lean conditions to reduce the production of pollutants, such as NO_x, are known to be prone to thermoacoustic instabilities, which in extreme cases lead to fatal failure of the engine [1]. It is well known that the mechanism leading these phenomena is the closure of a feedback loop between the noise produced by the flame and the response of the flame itself to acoustic waves [1, 2]. However, the prediction of such occurrences still remains a challenge. In this specific context, many tools have been developed to investigate thermoacoustic instabilities: from analytical models or low-order models [3–5] to the more expensive Large Eddy Simulation (LES) Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) tool. In the last two decades, LES has been applied to study combustion dynamics of purely gaseous flames in multiple regimes [6–9] and a comprehensive review of recent progress in the field of thermoacoustic combustion instabilities in propulsion engines can be found in [10, 11] for example.

When trying to reproduce the dynamic response of real systems, and more specifically of the next generation of aero-engines, it is important to take into account the injection of liquid fuel. In terms of modeling, tackling the problem of two-phase flows is a major issue. In the framework of thermoacoustic instabilities, a first computation of such a type was carried out by Innocenti *et al.* [12] using a Lagrangian formalism for the liquid phase coupled to the Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Simulations (URANS) to study the flame response to acoustic perturbations of a laboratory scale longitudinal aero-engine combustor. Although the trends are captured in terms of gain and phase, mismatches are present with respect to reported experimental data. A key aspect, in that case, is the capacity of properly taking into account the properties of the liquid phase and its dynamic response. Two numerical approaches can be applied to simulate the liquid phase. The first one relies on the resolution of an Eulerian system [13, 14] which is straightforward in terms of computational effort but reduces drastically the possibility to account for complex properties of sprays with large polydispersity for example. Eulerian approach has however already been applied with LES to study thermoacoustic instabilities in real configurations with satisfactory results when it comes to the main flow properties [15]. The second approach is to adopt the Lagrangian framework which solves the trajectory for each particle introducing difficulties such as load balancing because of the particles motion in the gaseous field [16] and their non-uniform distribution in the computa-

38 tional domain or the treatment when reaching the boundaries. Recently this
39 approach has been applied to many realistic LES applications with multiple
40 aims like ignition [17] or stabilized flames [18] as well as thermoacoustic in-
41 stabilities [19]. The importance of correctly reproducing the liquid droplet
42 behavior is in this case a key, since the feedback loop between the acoustic
43 field and the flame is coupled to the particle dynamics [20, 21]. Recent studies
44 have been performed to better understand this mechanism. For example Ki-
45 tano *et al* [22] studied particle dynamics during a thermoacoustic oscillation
46 for a laboratory step configuration linking the intensity of the thermoacous-
47 tic oscillation amplitude to the injected particle diameter, emphasizing how
48 phase change in the evaporation rate induced by the droplet size could impact
49 the instability. The academic test-case of a back-step flame was later studied
50 by Tachibana *et al.* [19] as a realistic aero-engine experimental setup, showing
51 again the importance of the fuel released by evaporation in the combustion
52 chamber with a direct effect on the evaporation rate fluctuations feeding the
53 heat-release rate and therefore driving the instability. However, results only
54 looked qualitatively satisfactory and the study showed quantitative discrep-
55 ancies in fluctuation amplitude and local flame behavior in part because of
56 the complexity of the geometry or errors in measurements. Note that for all
57 above mentioned studies the interaction between liquid particles and walls
58 are always simplified. The present work has for aim to show the impor-
59 tance of this feature in laboratory-scale applications aiming to reproduce the
60 physics of real combustion chambers. Indeed, in many aero-engine airblast
61 atomizers [23], the liquid fuel is injected at high pressure on a metal surface
62 called prefilmer with the aim of better atomizing the liquid fuel coming from
63 the pressurized tank [24]. The importance of correctly modeling this film to
64 reproduce thermoacoustic oscillations in real configurations needs to be eval-
65 uated. The physics of this process is however quite complex given the current
66 incapacity to experimentally visualize these regions in real applications or in
67 experimental setups with or without thermoacoustic instabilities.

68 This document is divided in four parts. First, in Sect. 2, the LES numeri-
69 cal methodology and the SICCA-spray configuration of EM2C are described.
70 Then, in Sect. 3.1, the cold flow is validated by comparison with measure-
71 ments while in Sect. 3.2 the steady flame results are analyzed with a first
72 sensitivity analysis to the treatment of the droplets boundary condition on
73 the injector wall. Finally, in Sect. 3.3, the dynamic response of the flame
74 is investigated in the self-excited limit-cycle condition of the SICCA-spray
75 burner [25]

Figure 1: SICCA-spray: experimental setup [26] (left) and numerical setup (right).

76 2. Numerical setup and Modeling

77 The SICCA-spray experimental setup, sketched in Fig. 1(left), is a single
 78 burner swirled spray n-heptane/air flame configuration [26]. It is a longi-
 79 tudinal setup where air flows from a plenum into a cylindrical combustion
 80 chamber equipped with a radial swirler. A typical hollow-cone shape atom-
 81 izer enables liquid fuel injection on the centerline of the swirler. Note that
 82 LDV measurements of the gaseous velocity profiles in cold conditions are per-
 83 formed without confinement for practical reasons. Moreover, the feedback
 84 loop between the flame and acoustics closes only when the chamber is longer
 85 than a threshold value [25]. To experience the self-sustained limit-cycle the
 86 quartz tube length was adapted to trigger this thermoacoustic oscillation
 87 modifying the first longitudinal mode of the chamber. For these reasons
 88 three different computational domains are used to mimic the three exper-
 89 iments operating with the same air mass flow rate, $\dot{m}_{air} = 2.58$ g/s, and
 90 global equivalence ratio, $\varphi = 0.85$, for the reactive cases:

- 91 • The cold case with an unconfined domain.

Figure 2: Mesh details for the SICCA-spray. The walls on the top right figure highlighted with the white dashed line are the ones where the spray impacts before entering the combustion chamber.

- 92 • The stable condition with $\ell_c = 165$ mm and for which the flame does
93 not present thermoacoustic oscillations.
- 94 • The limit-cycle condition with $\ell_c = 280$ mm where the system resonates
95 with a thermoacoustic mode.

96 Except for these geometrical changes, stable and unstable flames present
97 the same operating condition, mesh refinement and modeling as detailed
98 hereafter. The finest mesh zone is located at the injector exit so that the
99 reactive simulations correctly reproduce the flame root dynamics. In that
100 case, the stoichiometric n-heptane laminar flame thickness ($\delta_l=410 \mu\text{m}$) can
101 be used suggesting $\Delta x \simeq 150 \mu\text{m}$. Bigger cell sizes around $\Delta x \simeq 200 - 300$
102 μm are used further downstream near the combustion chamber exit and in
103 the injector zone while $\Delta x \simeq 500 \mu\text{m}$ in the swirler core (Fig. 2).

104 2.1. Gaseous phase modeling

105 The computational domain, Fig. 1(right), includes the atmosphere to cor-
106 rectly reproduce the acoustic boundary condition at the combustion chamber
107 outlet. To ease the flow establishment in this outer region a slow co-flow is
108 introduced to simulate the entrainment of the air by the combustor. The
109 main flow inlet locates in the plenum and corresponds for the simulations to
110 the hot wire location of the experiment (MC1 location on Fig. 1(left)).

Figure 3: Temperature axial profile on the combustion chamber wall in steady conditions. Comparison between external measurement (blue triangle), internal measurement (red square) and LES results (black solid line).

111 The simulations are performed using the code AVBP co-developed by
 112 CERFACS and IFPEN [27]. The fully compressible LES-filtered Navier-
 113 Stokes equations, enlisted in details in Appendix A, are solved using a
 114 third-order accurate in time and space Taylor-Galerkin scheme [28]. The
 115 Navier-Stokes Characteristic Boundary Conditions [29] are also used to treat
 116 the inlets and outlets of the simulations. According to theory [30], the inlet
 117 relaxation coefficient K used in this approach controls the magnitude and
 118 phase of the inlet reflection coefficient. For the steady flame calculations
 119 $K_{st} \simeq 1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is used. In the limit cycle case, starting from this value, K
 120 is reduced until a resonant condition is achieved for $K_{lc} \simeq 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which was
 121 verified to be still sufficient to avoid any mean value drift. The mass flow rate,
 122 \dot{m}_{air} , is fixed at the plenum with a turbulent mean profile, whereas for the co-
 123 flow a constant velocity of $w_{cofl} = 0.3 \text{ m/s}$ is imposed. For the atmospheric
 124 outlet, ambient pressure is imposed ($p = 101325 \text{ Pa}$ with $K_{out} = 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$).
 125 Walls are considered as no-slip and adiabatic except for the backplane and
 126 the combustion chamber wall where heat losses are not negligible in hot
 127 conditions [25]. In this case, the metal backplane of the combustion chamber
 128 is considered to be at a constant temperature of $T_{bkpl} = 450 \text{ K}$ and a small
 129 heat resistance of $R_{bkpl}^h = 1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2\text{K/W}$ is used to allow for heat to flow
 130 away from the surface. Regarding the combustion chamber wall, an axial
 131 temperature profile is imposed using the experimental data measured on the

132 external side of the combustion chamber. Imposing the correct value for
 133 the heat resistance based on the quartz thermal conductivity and the quartz
 134 width ($R_{chwl}^h = 1.38 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \text{ K/W}$), the temperature value on the inner
 135 wall becomes an output of the simulation, as verified in Fig. 3, which shows
 136 a correct agreement with internal measurements [25].

137 For all simulations, the turbulence subgrid model is WALE [31] and chem-
 138 ical reaction is described with the global two-step scheme *2S_C7H16_DP*
 139 involving 6 species and 2 reactions with pre-exponential adjustment (PEA)
 140 upon local equivalence ratio to correctly reproduce the laminar flame speed
 141 for rich mixtures [32]. For the present conditions, the premixed flame thick-
 142 ness is $\delta_L = 410 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, suggesting that with the mesh refinement in flame
 143 region used here a subgrid scale combustion model is needed. Here the
 144 TFLES model is employed but particular attention in a liquid fuel com-
 145 bustor is required. Indeed, as shown in a recent study by Rochette *et*
 146 *al.* [33], evaporation driven spray flames result in thicker reaction zones
 147 compared to their respective gaseous flames operating at the same equiv-
 148 alence ratio. Moreover, the combustion regime of two-phase flames is yet not
 149 well distinguished from the premixed and non-premixed conditions mean-
 150 ing that the application of a standard dynamic thickening factor affects the
 151 partially premixed or even diffusion flame. Here, the Takeno index [34],
 152 $TKN = \nabla Y_{C_7H_{16}} \cdot \nabla Y_{O_2} / |\nabla Y_{C_7H_{16}} \cdot \nabla Y_{O_2}|$ is used to locally detect the pre-
 153 mixed flame regions and apply a local thickening depending both on equiva-
 154 lence ratio and local resolution. Thickening is deactivated in diffusive flame
 155 regions. According to the TP-TFLES model [32] thickening is applied also on
 156 the evaporation rate since for two phase flames when modifying the charac-
 157 teristic chemical times t_{chem} implies the need of changing also the evaporation
 158 times t_{ev} .

159 2.2. Liquid phase modeling

160 A Lagrangian formalism is adopted to model the liquid spray. Droplet
 161 evolution forces are obtained using the Schiller-Neumann correlation for
 162 the droplet drag coefficient [35] while evaporation is modeled according to
 163 Abramzon and Sirignano [36]. The Prandtl and Schmidt numbers for the
 164 liquid phase are $Pr^{ev} = 0.976$ and $Sc^{ev} = 1.343$ for the evaporation process
 165 as in [37]. Two way coupling is considered for the liquid-gas interaction by
 166 use of a first order interpolation. The time integration for particle trajectory
 167 is obtained using two-step Runge-Kutta scheme so that $\Delta t_p = 2\Delta t$. The liq-
 168 uid particles are considered as much smaller than the LES grid size and their

169 deformation is negligible. Likewise gravity and shear effects are supposed
170 negligible compared to drag. The detailed formulation of the source terms
171 used to solve the LES equations for the liquid-gas phase coupling is reported
172 in Appendix A together with the closure terms for the droplet evaporation
173 and heat flux.

174 Addressing numerically liquid injection into the combustion chamber, and
175 capturing the specific liquid phase physics, is an open challenge. Hereafter,
176 the main characteristics of this physical phenomenon are summarized and
177 sketched in Fig. 4:

178 1. *Primary atomization:*

179 In the atomizer the liquid is injected through a high-pressure channel
180 and swirled. A film region is shaped as a hollow cone which creates
181 ligaments and big droplets because of high shear conditions.

182 2. *Secondary breakup:*

183 The liquid, subject to the aerodynamic field, is either further split into
184 smaller droplets and/or coalescence occurs between very small droplets.

185 3. *Splash:*

186 When a liquid spray impacts a wall, multiple complex interactions may
187 occur [38]. The particle properties, such as their size, temperature and
188 momentum strongly affect this phenomenon. The characteristics of
189 the surface, especially its temperature, roughness, wettability or the
190 presence of a film layer [39, 40] are also of importance in that case.

191 4. *Liquid-wall interaction:*

192 The liquid impacting the wall then forms a film which slides on the in-
193 jector wall until it reaches the combustion chamber where it is released.

194 5. *Edge atomization:*

195 At the edge of the injector, liquid fragmentation occurs because of
196 transverse instabilities in the flow.

197 6. *Unsteady injection model:*

198 In the context of thermoacoustic instabilities, the resonant coupling
199 between pressure and heat release may be linked to fluctuations of the
200 injected fuel mass flow rate [1]. The inclusion of this instability driving
201 mechanism requires the definition of an unsteady injection model.

202 In this work primary (1.) and secondary (2.) atomization phenomena
203 are not explicitly simulated but the semi-empirical model FIM-UR [41] is
204 used to prescribe a droplet diameter distribution at the atomizer orifice that

Figure 4: Sketch of the interaction between spray and turbulence before entering the combustion chamber.

205 enables to correctly reproduce the spray velocity and diameter distribution
 206 downstream the atomization process when the spray is diluted [42].

207 The atomizer parameters used in the experiment are $D_0 = 120 \mu\text{m}$ and
 208 $\Delta p \simeq 9 \text{ bar}$, translating in $\theta = 45^\circ$ for the injection model. Droplets are
 209 assumed to be at $T_{fuel} = 300 \text{ K}$ and a *Rosin-Rammler* probability function
 210 fitted on mean and Sauter diameters $D_{10} = 10 \mu\text{m}$ and $D_{32} = 18 \mu\text{m}$ respec-
 211 tively. These values are extracted from measurements at $z = 2.5 \text{ mm}$ from
 212 the chamber backplane [43]. The distribution being known in the simulation
 213 and fixed, the changes of diameter due to splash (3.), edge atomization (5.),
 214 primary (1.) and secondary (2.) atomization are not explicitly simulated.

215 Notice that the assumption of a constant value for both the cone angle
 216 and the liquid mass flow rate may not be verified when thermoacoustic os-
 217 cillations occur. However, the impact of thermoacoustic oscillations (6.) on
 218 the injection system itself can be neglected since the Δp of the atomizer is
 219 approximately one order of magnitude higher than the measured thermoa-
 220 coustic oscillations ($p' \simeq 1 - 2 \text{ kPa}$) so a constant liquid fuel mass flow rate,
 221 $\dot{m}_{fuel} = 0.144 \text{ g/s}$, imposed.

222 The present work focuses on the liquid-wall interaction (4.) and the
 223 numerical treatment of the film. Two particle-wall interaction treatments
 224 (summarized in Tab. 1) are tested and their impact on the spray-flame sta-
 225 bilization and the thermoacoustic combustion instabilities is evaluated:

- 226 • A slip condition [45] for which the wall normal velocity of the droplet is
 227 set to zero. As shown in Fig. 5 (a), droplets then stick to the wall and

Figure 5: Sketch of the two treatments for the liquid-wall interaction. (a) Slip condition: particles move independently on the wall (b). Film condition: the film velocity is the same for the whole set of particles moving on the wet surface.

228 their inertia moves each particle independently due to the local flow
 229 velocity.

- 230 • A film condition that accumulates the droplet in a Lagrangian liquid
 231 film layer whose depth and velocity are evaluated using Saint-Venant
 232 equations [44] as proposed in [46] and further developed in [47]. In
 233 that case, Fig. 5 (b), droplets are trapped by the film layer and start
 234 moving with a locally averaged velocity which corresponds to the film
 235 velocity and depends on the local shear stress and film height as well
 236 as the local volume of particles contained in the boundary cells where
 237 the model is activated. Particles are then released by the liquid sheet
 238 when an edge with angle higher than 60° is encountered.

239 The choice of this film boundary condition in the context of this study is
 240 supported by early experimental visualizations in the SICCA-spray chamber

Treatment	Characteristics
Slip	Particles reaching the walls slip along the wall at their initial speed
Film	Particles reaching the form a film. Its depth and speed are calculated using St. Venant equations [44]

Table 1: Wall treatments for the liquid fuel phase

241 where film ligaments have been clearly seen at the injector outlet under both
242 thermoacoustically stable and unstable conditions [43]. Unfortunately, since
243 the particle-wall interactions mainly happen inside the injector, no further
244 experimental data is available leaving the validation of these suggestions to
245 high-fidelity numerical simulations [25].

246 When it comes to the film modeling, details are provided hereafter. Start-
247 ing from the incompressible formulation, Navier-Stokes equations for the film
248 layer equations read

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad , \quad \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla p + \nu\nabla^2\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{g}. \quad (1)$$

249 Non-dimensional analysis and steady state assumptions for a 2D liquid sheet
250 produce

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dv}{dy} = 0 \\ v \frac{du}{dy} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dx} + \nu \frac{d^2u}{dy^2} + g \sin \gamma \\ \frac{dp}{dy} = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad \text{with} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \tau_w & y = h(x, t) \\ u = 0 & y = 0 \\ v = 0 & y = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

251 which together with closure at the film boundaries, $v = 0$ and $p = p_{ext}(x)$,
252 leads finally to

$$\nu \frac{d^2u}{dy^2} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dx} - g \sin \gamma \quad \text{with} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \tau_w & y=h(x, t) \\ u = 0 & y=0 \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

253 Once integrated the expression of u along the film thickness reads

$$u(y) = \left[\left(\frac{dp}{dx} - \rho g \sin \gamma \right) \left(\frac{y}{2} - h \right) + \tau_w \right] \frac{y}{\mu}. \quad (4)$$

254 Averaging the liquid velocity along its depth, and thus assuming locally the
 255 same velocity component for the whole set of particles contained in a bound-
 256 ary cell, one gets,

$$\bar{u}_f = \frac{1}{h} \int_0^h u(y) dy = \tau_w \frac{h}{2\mu} + \left(\rho g \sin \gamma - \frac{dp}{dx} \right) \frac{h^2}{3\mu}. \quad (5)$$

257 To better understand the physics behind the model, a first order expansion
 258 of the film thickness h without gravity or pressure gradient can be useful to
 259 recover a characteristic film velocity noted $U_{f,0}$ scaling and which follows

$$U_{f,0} \sim \tau_{w,0} \frac{h_0}{\mu_0}. \quad (6)$$

260 3. Results and discussion

261 In the first part of the following discussion the cold flow is analyzed. In
 262 the second part the steady-state reacting conditions are examined and the
 263 liquid droplet distribution validated. The effect of the treatment adopted for
 264 the liquid impinging the wall in the steady reactive case and with thermoacoustic
 265 instabilities will be presented and discussed in Sect. 3.2 and Sect. 3.3,
 266 respectively.

267 3.1. Cold flow conditions

268 Cold flow predictions are first addressed. To do so, for the purely gaseous
 269 jet, time ($t_{av} = 15$ ms) and angle average contours of axial, radial and tan-
 270 gential velocity components are respectively reported in Fig. 6. Figure 6 (a)
 271 shows that the swirled jet is characterized by a strong central recirculating
 272 zone (CRZ) and an outer recirculating zone (ORZ) limited by the black iso-
 273 line indicating the zero streamwise velocity. The jet opening is visualized
 274 from Fig. 6 (b) by the ORZ where the radial velocity pushes the cold gases
 275 in the corner through the jet axis. Figure 6 (c) visualizes the jet by showing
 276 the tangential velocity component. The validation of the aerodynamics of
 277 the gas phase is presented in Fig. 7 by comparing the jet mean profiles taken
 278 at $z = 2.5$ mm for the numerical prediction and the experiment. The axial
 279 velocity peak as well as the intensity of the CRZ are well captured by the LES
 280 (Fig. 7 (a)). A mismatch is observed on the peak position of the radial ve-
 281 locity component (Fig. 7 (b)) but since the tangential component, Fig. 7 (c),
 282 does show good agreement with the experimental values the underestimation

Figure 6: Axial, radial and tangential velocity components respectively U_z , U_r and U_θ ; time and angle average contours. (black line is $U_z = 0$, $U_r = 0$, $U_\theta = -1$).

283 of the jet opening is considered negligible. Indeed global quantities such as
 284 the swirl number of the jet and the injector head loss (reported in Tab. 2)
 285 are in good agreement with the experimentally reported values. confirming
 286 the appropriateness of the adopted mesh refinement.

Figure 7: Comparison between experiments [25] (symbols) and LES (solid line) at $z = 2.5$ mm from the chamber backplane for the velocity profiles [m/s]. Axial (a), radial (b) and tangential (c) components respectively.

287 Finally, to validate the modeling assumptions in terms of particle size
 288 distribution, using both the slip and film treatments, the droplet diameter
 289 is measured at $z = 2.5$ mm in the LES and the statistics are compared
 290 to the one obtained experimentally. Figure 8 shows that for both cases

	Equation	Experiment [25]	LES	Error
Head loss	$\Delta p = p_{max}^{pl} - p_{max}^{ch}$	3900 Pa	4092 Pa	5 %
Swirl number	$S = \frac{\int_0^R 2\pi\rho U_z U_\theta r^2 dr}{R \int_0^R 2\pi\rho U^2 r dr}$	0.55	0.51	7 %

Table 2: Global quantities of the cold flow, comparison between LES and experiments

Figure 8: PDF of particles diameter at $z = 2.5$ mm from the backplane of the chamber. Comparison between measured distribution and LES results in cold conditions for both the SLIP and FILM cases. Post-processing is done on a time window of 11 ms, $N_p = 11445$ obtaining $D_{10} = 10.4 \mu\text{m}$, $D_{32} = 18.2 \mu\text{m}$ in case of SLIP while on a time window of 13 ms and $N_p = 13387$ obtaining $D_{10} = 10.6 \mu\text{m}$, $D_{32} = 18.6 \mu\text{m}$ for FILM.

291 the particle diameter probability density function (PDF) collected from the
292 numerical simulation matches the one injected and therefore the experimental
293 measurements at that location.

294 3.2. Steady flame conditions

295 Figure 9 shows the instantaneous flame shapes obtained with the two
296 treatments (Tab. 1). Note that the two cases will be now referred to as SLIP
297 and FILM, respectively. Very similar characteristics are shown suggesting
298 a small impact on the mean flame topology of the wall-particle interaction
299 modeling. In Fig. 10, the complexity of this two-phase flame is empha-
300 sized by showing the contour of the Takeno index and total equivalence ratio
301 $\phi_{tot} = \phi + \phi_\ell$ where ϕ and ϕ_ℓ the gaseous and liquid equivalence ratios re-
302 spectively, with $\phi = sY_{C_7H_{16}}/Y_{O_2}$ where $s = 3.52$ is the stoichiometric ratio

Figure 9: Instantaneous flame shape in a y -normal plane: Heat release rate for cases SLIP (a) and FILM (b). The external contour of heat releases rate is $\dot{q} = 10 \text{ MW/m}^3$. In (b) $z_1 = 2.5 \text{ mm}$ and $z_2 = 50 \text{ mm}$ are indicated.

303 and $\phi_\ell = s\alpha_\ell/Y_{O_2}$, α_ℓ being the liquid volume fraction. For both cases, the
 304 flame root presents both premixed and diffusion regimes as expected when
 305 the evaporation is the leading process [33]. Moving downstream, the pre-
 306 mixed regime starts dominating in the center of the swirled jet where fuel
 307 vapor is trapped by the CRZ. On the external side of the hollow cone spray,
 308 combustion proceeds mainly in a diffusion regime due to the presence in that
 309 region of larger droplets and lower gas temperature induced by the ORZ.

d_p [μm]	T [K]	500	750	1000	1250	1500	1750
5		0.23	0.12	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.04
10		0.94	0.47	0.32	0.25	0.2	0.17
20		3.74	1.88	1.29	1	0.81	0.69

Table 3: Evaporation time t_{ev} [ms] for n-heptane droplets at $T_p = 300 \text{ K}$ and ambient pressure.

310 Table 3 displays the evaporation times for different gas temperatures and
 311 droplet diameters. Because of the high volatility of n-heptane, the liquid
 312 phase evaporation times are very fast as long as the particle diameter remains
 313 small. However, for particles with diameters larger than $d_p = 10 \mu\text{m}$ (e.g.,
 314 see the last line in Tab. 3) the evaporation time t_{ev} and the convective time
 315 $t_w = 1.52 \text{ ms}$ needed to reach $z = 50 \text{ mm}$, evaluated using the bulk velocity

Figure 10: Y-normal plane: Takeno index in the flame region for the SLIP (a) and FILM (c) cases. Total equivalence ratio ϕ_{tot} for SLIP (b) and FILM (d) cases. The external contour of heat releases rate is $\dot{q} = 10 \text{ MW/m}^3$.

316 at the combustion chamber entrance $U_b \simeq 40 \text{ m/s}$, become comparable. This
 317 confirms that large droplets can reach the flame tip, following the hollow
 318 cone trajectory, as visible from the spots at high ϕ_{tot} in Fig. 10. Note that
 319 such large droplets crossing the flame should burn in an isolated droplet
 320 combustion regime. However, the number of such particles remains negligible
 321 so that the modeling tailored for this specific phenomenon is neglected.

322 Figure 11 displays a scatter plot of gas temperature versus mixture frac-
 323 tion $Z = \frac{sY_{C_7H_{16}} - Y_{O_2} + Y_{O_2}^0}{sY_{C_7H_{16}}^0 + Y_{O_2}}$ for both cases. For this diagnostic, the whole
 324 instantaneous flame is taken into account, that is to say all points inside the
 325 white contour of Fig. 9 are considered. For both cases the flame structure
 326 is very similar, the flame being mostly burning in a premixed regime (red
 327 scatter) following the adiabatic flamelet until the lean combustion limit is
 328 reached and the temperature decreases drastically ($Z \simeq 0.04 \rightarrow \phi \simeq 0.6$).
 329 As expected, the flame in the non-premixed regime burns mainly at stoi-
 330 chiometry while the low temperature points of this combustion regime are
 331 probably linked to the two-phase flame which broadens the presence of such
 332 a front via evaporation.

333 Angle and time-average ($t_{av} = 30 \text{ ms}$) fields of heat release rate are then
 334 compared to experimental Abel transforms of CH^* chemiluminescence [25]
 335 in Fig. 12. Fairly satisfactory agreement in terms of flame shape and spatial

(a)

(b)

Figure 11: Scatter plot of the flame structure in the $T - Z$ plane for the SLIP (a) and FILM (b) cases. The color refers to different values of the Takeno index selecting the flame burning in premixed (red) or diffusive (blue) regimes. The two gray vertical line indicate the stoichiometric mixture fraction $Z^{st} = 0.062$ (dashed) and the one corresponding to the global equivalence ratio $Z^{85} = 0.0527$ (dotted), whereas the two adiabatic equilibrium lines are reported in black.

336 distribution of the flame intensity is found for both cases. A slight under-
 337 estimation of the flame opening is visible especially in the tip region but
 338 unless further information regarding the spray characteristics and diameter
 339 distribution is available, improvement seems difficult to obtain.

340 Focusing now on the liquid fuel properties, using the same time and angle

Figure 12: Comparison between LES angle and time-averaged flame shape, on the left, and CH* chemiluminescence, on the right for SLIP (a) and FILM (b) cases.

Figure 13: Angle and time averaged particles diameter distribution for SLIP (a) and FILM (b) cases.

341 average post-processing, the spatial distribution of particle diameters is pre-

342 sented in Fig. 13: both flames produce a *tulip-shape* rather than an *M-flame*
 343 because of the droplet distribution in the chamber.

Figure 14: Liquid fuel properties at $z = 2.5$ mm from the backplane. Scatter of particles axial velocity compared with the gas mean profile (dashed line) for SLIP (a) and FILM (b) cases. Post-processing is done as in Fig. 8.

344 Figure 14 shows the axial velocity profiles at $z = 2.5$ mm of the fuel particles
 345 grouped in four ranges of size. The dashed line represents the mean
 346 gaseous velocity at this same location. Regardless of the wall-interaction
 347 treatment, one observes that particles are mainly driven by the gaseous phase
 348 with the exception of the droplets with $d_p > 10 \mu\text{m}$ (reported in black di-
 349 amonds) which detach from smaller particles due to inertia effects. It is
 350 also worth noting that these large droplets mainly locate on the outer tip

Figure 15: (a) Sketch of the two particles trajectories in a cut containing the symmetry axis. Liquid volume fraction $\rho_\ell \alpha_\ell$ for the SLIP (a) and FILM (b) cases.

351 part of the flame which will then favor the isolated droplet flames identified
 352 previously.

353 To further compare droplet trajectory, the liquid volume fraction $\rho_\ell \alpha_\ell$ is
 354 displayed on a plane, containing the symmetry axis of the jet, in Fig. 15 for
 355 the SLIP (b) and FILM (c) cases respectively. One can see that particle
 356 trajectories can be of two different types, as sketched in Fig. 15 (a): most
 357 of the liquid phase injected hits the nearby injector wall (group \mathcal{P}_A) and
 358 only a small number of droplets follows the aerodynamic flowing directly
 359 in the combustion chamber (group \mathcal{P}_B). Note that the two different wall-
 360 interaction treatments will have an impact only on the droplets of the first
 361 group being the ones impinging the wall. Focusing the attention on this
 362 portion of liquid fuel, the effect of the different treatments can be observed
 363 comparing Fig. 15 (b) with (c). In the SLIP case, the liquid follows the
 364 angle of the injector wall after being detached at the edge and entering the
 365 combustion chamber, while for the FILM the detachment is regulated by the
 366 film model and the particles follow the flow without any previous inertial
 367 effect.

368 To conclude, the results presented in this section show that the treatment
 369 of the interaction between particles and walls does not have a major impact
 370 on the steady flame. The two simulations indeed show similar results and
 371 flame shapes as well as a similar dynamics of the liquid fuel in the combustion

372 chamber, confirming that the aerodynamic field is the primary driver for the
 373 present particle distribution. The flame structure is also very similar in
 374 terms of combustion regimes and equivalence ratio spatial distribution, the
 375 field being mainly governed by the evaporation process. Differences mainly
 376 appear in the injection system. Depending on the particle-wall interaction
 377 model retained, the liquid fuel released at the edge of the injector seem to
 378 have different momentum. Therefore small changes in droplet trajectories
 379 can arise as shown by Fig. 15 but without impacting the flame regime or the
 380 anchoring process.

381 3.3. Thermoacoustic self-excited condition

Figure 16: Pressure fluctuation measured at the combustion chamber backplane with a zoom on some cycles showing how the unsteady pressure and heat release rate oscillations present the same phase satisfying the Rayleigh criterion.

382 The dynamic response of the two particle-wall treatment is now discussed
 383 in the context of thermo-acoustic combustion instabilities. In this case, the
 384 two stable flames described in the Sect. 2 are considered but with a longer
 385 flame tube, a configuration in which a self-sustained limit cycle is observed
 386 in the experiment [25].

387

388 The limit cycle

389

390 Figure 16 (left) shows the temporal evolution of the pressure fluctuation
 391 evolution registered by a sensor located on the combustion chamber back-
 392 plane when the film treatment is used (case FILM). At the beginning of
 393 this specific simulation, the pressure signal features a classical exponential

Figure 17: Acoustic mode obtained with Helmholtz solver.

394 increase until a maximum pressure value (overshoot point) is reached [48].
 395 The pressure oscillation then decreases until the energy generated by the
 396 thermo-acoustic coupling equals the system damping. Again for this specific
 397 case, after $t = 0.12$ s, the thermoacoustic oscillation can be considered
 398 established and a steady limit cycle condition is reached. A zoom on the
 399 simulation signal at latter time, Fig. 16 (right), shows indeed that the fluctu-
 400 ation of pressure and heat release are approximately in phase, satisfying the
 401 Rayleigh criterion [49] as expected in a thermo-acoustically unstable con-
 402 dition. It should be also noted that in the combustion chamber the level
 403 of the limit cycle, $p'_{LES} \simeq 2000$ Pa, is in line with the experimental mea-
 404 surements where a fluctuation amplitude of $p'_{exp} \simeq 1700$ Pa is recorded [25].
 405 Finally, the self-sustained operating condition yields a numerical oscillation
 406 at $f_{LES} \simeq 500$ Hz in decent agreement with the reported experimental value
 407 of $f_{EXP} = 530$ Hz [25].

408 A preliminary simulation with the Helmholtz solver AVSP [50] was per-
 409 formed in passive flame conditions assuming cold conditions for the plenum
 410 and an average temperature of 1500 K in the combustion chamber (based on
 411 the LES simulations of the steady flame). To account for the scattering effect
 412 at the outlet, following previous works dealing with the same problem (e.g.,
 413 see Ref [51] where an experimentally measured end-correction was applied to
 414 a annular combustion chamber to correctly retrieve the resonant mode fre-
 415 quencies), the combustion chamber length has been augmented by $l_{cc,corr} =$
 416 $0.6 r_{cc} = 21$ [mm], which is the typical end-correction value for an unflanged
 417 circular pipe [52]. A pressure node condition ($p'=0$) is then imposed at the
 418 new outlet boundary. For sake of simplicity, a fully reflective inlet with $R=1$
 419 is imposed at the inlet. A resonant mode with a frequency of $f \simeq 530$ Hz
 420 is retrieved from the eigenvalue analysis, value close to the one at which the

Figure 18: Heat release rate phase average, colormap: $\dot{q} \in [0, 250]$ MW/m³, comparison with the experimental CH* chemiluminescence [25].

421 numerical (and experimental) limit cycle occurs ($f_{LES} \simeq 500$ Hz). This re-
 422 sult indicates that the observed dynamics are not associated to an intrinsic
 423 instability of the flame but they have an acoustic origin [53, 54].

424 In terms of flame shape, to remove random oscillations due to turbulence
 425 and retrieve only the coherent limit cycle oscillation, LES results are first
 426 phase-averaged over 10 cycles (Fig. 18). For each phase of the cycle, an
 427 angle average procedure is then performed. Note that in the following, the
 428 phase $\Phi \in [0, 2\pi]$ refers to the pressure signal oscillation for which $\Phi = \pi/2$
 429 corresponds to the positive peak of heat release. Simulation results are finally
 430 compared to the experimental views from EM2C laboratory [25] in Fig. 18
 431 proving the good agreement during the whole cycle for the overall flame
 432 shape, its extent as well as its anchoring position.

433 To conclude, even if a detailed comparison with the experimental data is
 434 out of the scope for this work, the LES and the experiment are found in fair
 435 agreement in terms of frequency, nature and combustion chamber pressure
 436 fluctuations confirming the validity of the modeling assumptions.

437

438 Modeling effect on the prediction

439

440 In agreement with the observations obtained for steady operating condi-
 441 tion, the same calculation as the one discussed above is repeated changing
 442 only the particle-wall treatment: *i.e.* using the slip treatment in place of the
 443 film model (case SLIP). For the discussion, both transients are compared in
 444 Fig. 19, with (a) the time trace of the chamber pressure fluctuation for the
 445 backplane probe, (b) the fluctuating heat release rate per unit volume. In
 446 case of the SLIP condition traces of coherent oscillations are visible in the
 447 recorded pressure fluctuation as shown in Fig. 19 (a)(black line) for latter

Figure 19: Comparison between the FILM and SLIP cases in resonating conditions. (a) Pressure fluctuation of the combustion chamber backplane as obtained for the two modeling approaches as well as (b) the temporal evolution of the heat release rate fluctuations. Both quantities are given as a function of time starting from the same initial flame and only the liquid-wall interaction treatment differs.

448 times. However, the mode growth observed in the previous simulation is
 449 not recovered and the oscillation amplitude remains very small and intermit-
 450 tent if compared to the one obtained using the film treatment (gray line in
 451 Fig. 19 (a)). More interestingly, coherence in the fluctuating heat release rate
 452 signal disappears very early in the SLIP case, as shown in Fig. 19 (b)(red
 453 line), while the film modeling provides sufficient response at longer times.

454 The absence of predominant oscillation frequency with the slip condition
 455 film treatment is verified by Fig. 20 (a) which shows the spectra of the heat
 456 release rate obtained for both simulations. The FFT confirms that the slip
 457 condition does not lead to a full synchronization of the heat release rate with
 458 the nearby acoustic mode. Indeed, multiple frequencies coexist including
 459 lower and higher than the 500 Hz contribution which, instead, remains weak if
 460 compared to the other simulation. Indeed, in the case of SLIP, the system and
 461 the harmonic oscillation last only for a short period of time. Figure 20 (b)
 462 which shows the superposition of the pressure time trace along with the
 463 fluctuating heat release as a function of the same time interval, confirms that
 464 the Rayleigh criterion is never fully satisfied but instead can be occasionally
 465 negative contrarily to the first simulation, as seen from Fig. 16. Using the
 466 film model instead, the system produces a coherent oscillation at $f_{LES} \simeq 500$

467 Hz (to be compared with the experimental value of $f_{EXP} = 530$ Hz [25]).

468 To eliminate any uncertainty regarding the initial condition another test
 469 was performed targeting the use of the slip treatment for droplets impinging
 470 the wall. Starting from the self-sustained unstable condition obtained with
 471 the film treatment, at time $t_{sw} \simeq 0.07$ s this film particle-wall interaction
 472 treatment is switched to slip. Looking at the corresponding temporal evolu-
 473 tion presented in Fig. 21, the pressure fluctuation in the chamber backplane
 474 clearly gets damped after ten cycles and the system eventually reaches the
 475 same quasi-steady state as the one obtained previously. This second test is
 476 in the following used to better understand the effect of the film modeling by
 477 looking at the evolution of the liquid fuel distribution and properties inside
 478 the injection system at two specific instants and for the two cases of FILM ad
 479 SLIP. To do so, the liquid volume fraction α_l is plotted for the two instants:
 480 *i.e.* $t_1 = t_{sw} + 3\mathcal{T}$ and $t_2 = t_{sw} + 10\mathcal{T}$, with \mathcal{T} the period of the thermoacoustic
 481 oscillation. Comparing the two different treatments, one notes that
 482 the amount of fuel trapped inside the system is kept almost constant after
 483 10 cycles when the film modeling is adopted, Fig. 22 (a-b). On the contrary,
 484 when the condition is slip, particles are still in the injector 3 cycles after t_{sw} ,
 485 Fig. 22 (c), but these trapped particles are rapidly washed away by the strong
 486 aerodynamics oscillations and after few other cycles, Fig. 22 (d). The injec-
 487 tor wall is almost clean of particles except nearby the edge at latter times.

Figure 20: (a) FFT of the unsteady heat release rate using the two different cases and (b) unsteady heat release and pressure fluctuation for the SLIP case.

Figure 21: Pressure fluctuation signal at chamber back-plane when the treatment is switched from film to slip.

488 This brings to the conclusion that as long as droplets are trapped in the near
 489 injector region the oscillation remains high, but as soon as the slip condi-
 490 tion prevails, the liquid trapped in this region starts entering the combustion
 491 chamber without the adequate delay which precludes a clear establishment
 492 of the oscillation.

493 Focusing now on the distribution of liquid volume fraction α_l at the edge
 494 of the injector shown in Fig. 22, droplet behaviours and therefore the thermo-
 495 acoustic response of the system mainly appears to be controlled by the
 496 chosen wall treatment. Indeed, in case SLIP, Fig. 22 (c-d) shows that, at
 497 longer times, after impacting with the wall, particles penetrate the main
 498 stream jet entering the combustion chamber closer to the jet axis before be-
 499 ing accelerated by the radial component of the jet. This is not the case when
 500 the film treatment is adopted, Fig. 22 (a-b).

501 Figure 23 shows the droplet velocity magnitude confirming once more
 502 that the application of a slip model does not slow down the liquid impinging
 503 the wall before entering the combustion chamber. Note from Fig. 23 (c) that
 504 some particles although being part of the remaining film layer, already at
 505 time t_1 , present high velocities in the combustion chamber $|\vec{v}_p| \geq 30$ m/s. At
 506 latter times even faster particles appear, Fig. 23 (d), and the presence of high
 507 speed droplets further downstream in the combustion chamber increases the
 508 stiffness to the external modulation of the liquid fuel entering the combustion

Figure 22: Liquid volume fraction, $\rho_\ell \alpha_\ell$, at $t_1 = 0.078$ ms and $t_2 = 0.1$ ms for the simulations for FILM (a)-(b) and SLIP (c)-(d) cases.

509 chamber. Its propensity to couple with the thermoacoustic oscillation is
 510 therefore reduced.

511 As shown in the next section, the difference of relative velocity between
 512 the liquid and the gaseous phase near the walls helps triggering the thermoacoustic
 513 mode of this configuration. In that respect, only the film treatment
 514 is able to reproduce the proper effect, being the response of the film affected
 515 by the acoustic oscillation. The slip condition instead is not able to capture
 516 this complex dynamics letting the droplets enter the combustion chamber
 517 without being modulated by the presence of acoustics in the system.

518

519 Effect of the film on the thermoacoustic loop

520

521 The previous analysis suggests the fundamental importance of the film re-
 522 sponse in the presence of an external acoustic field. Assuming that the local
 523 aerodynamics is the same for both simulations, the quantity characterizing
 524 the film response is its thickness, h_f . Figure 24 (a) displays the film thickness
 525 fluctuation h' as a function of the film coordinate ξ (*cf.* Fig. 15 (a)) and ob-
 526 tained at different instants in the limit-cycle period of the simulation . This

Figure 23: Liquid velocity magnitude, \vec{v}_p , at $t_1 = 0.078 \text{ ms}$ and $t_2 = 0.1 \text{ ms}$ respectively for the simulations for FILM (a)-(b) and SLIP (c)-(d) cases.

527 quantity is clearly fluctuating within an envelop corresponding to the phase
528 $\Phi = 0$ and 2π if referring to the definition introduced for Fig. 18. The other
529 observation is that this film layer only responds to acoustics in its second
530 half, that is for $\xi \in [4.5, 7]$, where large variations of h' are achieved. Based
531 on such observations, some interesting quantities relative to this film oscillation
532 as its characteristic frequency, noted f_f , can be proposed. First, taking
533 the average film velocity along the axial film coordinate ξ , $U_f \simeq 1.3 \text{ m/s}$, and
534 considering the length of the oscillating film layer only, $l_f^{osc} = 2.5 \text{ mm}$, the
535 film characteristic frequency reads $f_f = U_f/l_f = 520 \text{ Hz}$. This simple evaluation
536 confirms that during the limit cycle the film response synchronization
537 with the thermoacoustic loop appears. The response of the film is further
538 confirmed by Fig. 24 (b) where the phase averaged film thickness fluctuation
539 is shown as a function of the mode acoustic pressure phase during the cycle
540 and for various axial locations within the film. Clearly only the second
541 half of the film exhibits thickness variations that are in phase with the local
542 pressure signal identified as p'/\bar{p} in Fig. 24 (b).

543 Figure 25(a) reports the fluctuation of the non-dimensional equivalence
544 ratio at an axial station near the flame root ($z = 2.5 \text{ mm}$). If compared with

Figure 24: (a) Non-dimensional film height fluctuation, h'/\bar{h} , along the film local coordinate ξ during the period of oscillation. (b) Non-dimensional film height fluctuation, h'/\bar{h} , measured at different locations along the film, plot in phase with the mode pressure signal p'/\bar{p} properly rescaled.

545 the previously discussed film thickness dynamics (Fig. 24(a)), it is possible to
 546 notice that the two variables oscillate in phase (to improve the visualisation
 547 of this result, the curves corresponding to $\phi = \pi/2$ and $\phi = 3/2\pi$ have the
 548 same color in both images). An explanation of this result is retrieved recalling
 549 the film modelling presented in Sec. 2.2. As indicated by Eq. (6), film
 550 thickness fluctuation and constant wall shear stress result in a film velocity
 551 fluctuation and therefore the release of particles at the edge of the injector
 552 with different particle velocities but more importantly function of the acoustic
 553 signal. Figure 25 (a) shows as a consequence the fluctuation of equivalence
 554 ratio near the flame root ($\phi'/\bar{\phi}$, full lines) and the film velocity fluctuation
 555 (u'/\bar{u} , dashed line) at two radial coordinates of the lines shown in Fig.25(a)
 556 near the injector lip. As intuited above both quantities are in phase revealing
 557 the major impact on the fuel feeding of the flame root dynamics. In other
 558 words the feedback to the thermoacoustic mode involves the film response
 559 which needs to be taken into account through modeling. Indeed, the film
 560 thickness and therefore the particle velocity composing the film introduce a
 561 dependency of the fuel feeding process of the combustion chamber, the heat
 562 release and potentially the system pressure fluctuation field.

563 In Fig. 26, fields of heat release (a) are provided along with fields of
 564 total equivalence ratio (b) at various phases of the obtained numerical pre-
 565 diction. In agreement with the scenario detailed previously, higher levels

Figure 25: (a) Non-dimensional equivalence ratio fluctuations, $\phi'/\bar{\phi}$, as a function of the radial coordinate x , measured at the flame root ($z = 2.5$ mm) during the period of oscillation. (b) Non-dimensional equivalence ratio fluctuations, $\phi'/\bar{\phi}$, at the flame root plot in phase with film velocity fluctuations, u'/\bar{u} , at the edge of the film layer.

566 of heat release fluctuations coincide with the release by the film of a large
567 number of particles in the chamber ($\Phi \in [0 - \pi]$). On the contrary at latter
568 times ($\Phi = [\pi, 2\pi]$), the swirler flow aerodynamics pushes the flow back in
569 the combustion chamber the CRZ almost vanishing. For this part of the
570 cycle, the flame shortens consuming the gaseous fuel present in the chamber
571 ($\Phi = 3\pi/2$) the fresh fuel being trapped in the injection system and the film,
572 until $\Phi = 17\pi/10$ where the heat release rate increases again entering a new
573 cycle.

574 A final observation of interest focuses on the overall fluid mechanics re-
575 sponse of the system and its effect on the particle distribution within the
576 combustion chamber during the cycle. As indicated previously, the film is a
577 key element in determining the proper response of SICCA-spray but so does
578 the aerodynamics and more particularly the fuel distribution, both evapo-
579 rated and liquid, in the combustor. To evidence and emphasize this last
580 aspect Fig. 27 (a) displays the temporal evolution of the fluctuating number
581 of particles around the mean and presents their evolution for different axial
582 planes away from the chamber backplane. For the lower planes, *i.e.* in the in-
583 jector exit region or $z = 2.5\&4$ mm away from the chamber backplane, more
584 droplets are released in the early instants of the mode in agreement with
585 previous findings: *i.e.* in phase with the reference pressure signal. Further
586 away in the chamber, *i.e.* $z = 9\&14$ mm, the response is out of phase with

Figure 26: Phase averaged (a) heat release distribution and (b) overall equivalent ration during the limit cycle; added contours indicate the $\dot{q} = 50$ MW/m³ release rate location.

587 the pressure signal indicating that either the number of droplets initially
588 injected are consumed, and/or evaporated, or it takes them time to reach
589 this position. Looking at the fluctuation of D_{10} , Fig. 27 (b), one notes the
590 opposite occurs if compared to the number of liquid droplets in Fig. 27 (a).
591 The fluctuation of D_{10} is however more difficult to describe. On one hand,
592 focusing in the near injector region where D_{10} is in phase opposition with the
593 droplet number, one concludes that either smaller droplets are evaporated
594 rapidly and/or larger particles are absent at this location. Conversely, far
595 from the combustion backplane, at these same instants more droplets are
596 present and apparently most likely characterized by large diameters empha-
597 sizing the potential importance of the evaporation rate of the large droplets.

598 4. Conclusions

599 The lean two-phase swirled flames of the SICCA-spray experiment is
600 simulated by use of a Lagrangian LES formalism for both the steady and
601 self-sustained limit-cycle operating conditions. For this specific burner, the
602 capability of the Lagrangian approach to fully represent these problems is

(a)

(b)

Figure 27: Fluctuations of the droplets number (a) and mean diameter D_{10} (b) during the limit cycle at different location from the backplane.

603 shown to be for the latter dependent on the use of a film model while it is
 604 seen to be insensitive to this modeling for the former. Indeed, the use of
 605 a more standard slip condition for the liquid particles impinging the walls
 606 is shown to be a valid option for the steady result. However, it does not
 607 allow to successfully reproduce the dynamics of the system and the thermo-
 608 acoustic instability, leading to limit cycle, observed experimentally. For this
 609 specific operating condition, the two modeling strategies are detailed and to
 610 evidence how the slip treatment is stabilizing the system. In both cases, *i.e.*
 611 when the instability is willing to occur or when the unstable regime is al-
 612 ready established, the case SLIP results in a system that gets damped after

613 few cycles with fluctuation levels that are rapidly far from the experimental
614 observations and not self-sustained. Only in case of FILM, when introducing
615 a specific film velocity imposed to the particles trapped in the injector wall,
616 the experimental observations are accurately reproduced. The capability of
617 the film treatment to adapt the liquid sheet properties to the self-sustained
618 oscillation indicates that the fuel film layer is responding to the external flow
619 fluctuations ensuring a closed feedback loop with the thermoacoustics of the
620 entire system and therefore the establishment of the self-sustained limit-cycle.

621 Acknowledgements and Fundings

622 This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020
623 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant
624 agreement No 765998 in the project ANNULIGH T. The authors gratefully
625 acknowledge the financial support from Agence Nationale de la Recherche
626 (ANR) under the project FASMIC (ANR16-CE22-0013). D. Laera is grate-
627 ful to the European Union Horizon 2020 for financial support under the
628 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship grant agreement No 843958
629 in the project CLEANERFLAMES. This work was performed using HPC
630 resources from GENCI-CINES. Particular gratitude goes to T. Laroche and
631 J. Carmona who participated with useful discussions and active effort in
632 optimizing the film boundary condition and to the whole CERFACS team
633 developing AVBP. The authors also thank Daniel Durox and the team per-
634 forming experiments at EM2C in Paris for the availability and the share of
635 data and ideas.

636 Appendix A. The code AVBP with Euler-Lagrange formalism

637 The LES code AVBP solves the full compressible Navier-Stokes equations
638 with spatial filtering:

$$\frac{D}{Dt}(\bar{\rho}\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) = -\nabla \cdot (\bar{p}\mathbf{I} - \bar{\mathbf{T}} - \bar{\mathbf{T}}^{sgs}) + \bar{\mathbf{s}}_M \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\frac{D}{Dt}(\bar{\rho}E) = -\nabla \cdot (\overline{\mathbf{u} \cdot p\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{T}} + \bar{\mathbf{q}} + \bar{\mathbf{q}}^{sgs}) + \bar{\mathbf{s}}_E \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\frac{D}{Dt}(\bar{\rho}\tilde{Y}_k) = -\nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{j}}_k + \bar{\mathbf{j}}_k^{sgs}) + \bar{\mathbf{s}}_{Y_k} \quad k = 1, N_S \quad (\text{A.3})$$

641 where the Favre filtering $\tilde{f} = \overline{\rho f} / \bar{\rho}$ weights with density the Reynolds filtered
642 variables \bar{f} . $\frac{D}{Dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \nabla$ is the total derivative, \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix
643 and the terms $\bar{\dot{\mathbf{s}}}_M$, $\bar{\dot{\mathbf{s}}}_E$ and $\bar{\dot{\mathbf{s}}}_{Y_k}$ are the exchange terms between gaseous and
644 liquid phase. $\bar{\mathbf{T}}$ is the filtered stress tensor, $\bar{\mathbf{j}}_k$ is the species flux according
645 to [48] while $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$ accounts of heat fluxes due to differential diffusion of species
646 and temperature. Subgrid scale closure is modelled as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}}^{sgs} = \bar{\rho}(\widetilde{\mathbf{u} : \mathbf{u}} - \tilde{\mathbf{u}} : \tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \simeq 2\bar{\rho}\nu_t \left(\tilde{\mathbf{S}} - \frac{1}{3}tr(\tilde{\mathbf{S}})\mathbf{I} \right) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

647

$$\bar{\mathbf{j}}_k^{sgs} = \bar{\rho}(\widetilde{Y_k \mathbf{u}} - \tilde{Y}_k \tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \simeq 2\bar{\rho} \left(D_t \frac{W_k}{W} \nabla \tilde{X}_k - \tilde{Y}_k \mathbf{V}^c \right) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

648

$$\bar{\mathbf{q}}^{sgs} = \bar{\rho}(\widetilde{E \mathbf{u}} - \tilde{E} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \simeq -\lambda_t \nabla \tilde{T} + \sum_{k=1}^{N_S} \bar{\mathbf{j}}_k^{sgs} \tilde{h}_{s,k} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

649 where the turbulent eddy viscosity ν_t is computed according to [31] and the
650 coefficients for species and temperature are computed imposing the turbulent
651 Prandtl and Schmidt numbers to 0.6 from $D_t = \nu_t / Sc^t$ and $\lambda_t = \bar{\rho} \nu_t \overline{C_p} / Pr^t$.
652 The Lagrangian formalism for the liquid phase reads

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_p \quad , \quad \frac{d\mathbf{u}_p}{dt} = \frac{\mathbf{f}_p}{m_p} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

653 where \mathbf{x}_p is the particle position, \mathbf{u}_p its velocity, m_p its mass and \mathbf{f}_p the sum
654 of forces acting on each particles which here is considered to be drag only.
655 Evaporation is handles by a mass balance such as

$$\frac{dm_p}{dt} = \dot{m}_p \quad , \quad \frac{dT_p}{dt} = -\frac{1}{m_p C_{p,l}} \phi_p^c \quad (\text{A.8})$$

656 where \dot{m}_p is the evaporation rate, $C_{p,l}$ the liquid specific heat and ϕ_p^c the
657 conductive heat flux to be exchanged with the gaseous phase.
658 The exchange terms assume the form [55]

$$\bar{\dot{\mathbf{s}}}_M = -\frac{1}{V} \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} w_{p@n} (\dot{m}_p \mathbf{u}_p + \mathbf{f}_p) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

659

$$\bar{\dot{\mathbf{s}}}_E = -\frac{1}{V} \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} w_{p@n} \left(\phi_p^c - \dot{m}_p h_{s,F}(T_p) + \frac{1}{2} \dot{m}_p \mathbf{u}_p^2 + \mathbf{f}_p \cdot \mathbf{u}_p \right) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

660

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}}_{Y_k} = -\frac{1}{V} \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} w_{p@n} (\dot{m}_p \delta_{k,F}) \quad (\text{A.11})$$

661 where $w_{p@n}$ is the conservative weight for the particle p with respect the
 662 node n , ϕ^c is the heat flux from at the droplet surface such that $\phi_p^c = -\phi^c +$
 663 $\dot{m}_p L_v(T_p)$ with L_v the droplet latent heat of vaporization. Closure for the
 664 evaporation term \dot{m}_p and for the flux term ϕ^c is given by

$$\dot{m}_p = -\pi d \text{Sh} [\rho D_F] \ln(1 + B_M) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

665

$$\phi^c = -\pi d \text{Nu} \lambda (T_\infty - T_p) \frac{\ln(1 + B_T)}{B_T} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

666 as in [56], [57] with B_M and B_T the Spalding numbers of mass and temper-
 667 ature according to [58].

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